

**ENGINEERING INSTITUTIONS' CAMPUS RECRUITMENT
TENDENCY AND DISPUTES – A Study in Coimbatore City
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Abstract:

It has happened a generation ago, the young student has graduated from colleges, chosen a job and it has turned into a career for lifetime. They were given with loyalty and the situation for switchover from the present job has not aroused. Many opportunities were availed for switching over from the present job in the ladder of corporate while the increasing of prestige and mainly for salary. The recruitment has been taken as a function and it has evolved and has grown diversely at various levels. So it has become a vital and very crucial thing for all the entities which have an effective and systematic Recruiting Plan. But at the same time, many Educational Institutions have introduced the innovative methods of teaching by downing the practical approach. With this they are making the students market ready. The campus recruitment at any Educational Institutions is the most critical task and its main aim is all about making the students as a long-term investment for the stakeholders and also for the benefit of the entities for the future success¹. There are many olden ways of using the recruitment from campus by corporate, educational institutions, body corporates and students in India. In order to make this way of recruitment as an effective and meaningful there are various models are availed and also adopted by many Educational Institutions, Body corporates and Corporates. The importance of reaching out the students' community with the help of several forums has been realized by the organizations². Hiring and recruiting the correct resources from the Engineering Educational Institutions is a high risky and critical task for all the business corporates. This task becomes a tougher one when the talent is in raw stage and the need is focused on grooming. Hence, the present study focused on the Engineering Institutions' campus recruitment tendency and disputes. Both primary and secondary sources of data have been used for successful completion of the study.

Key Words: Loyalty, Hiring Plan, Stakeholders, Educational Bodies & Right Resources and Engagement Forums.

Introduction:

The problem of unemployment is up today, there is a scarcity in job and the layoffs has become a common across in the organizations. The techno human resources has developing as a process in Engineering Educational Institutions. This techno human resources has been used later as *input* to the industries which has been turned its process of producing the goods and services for the societal use. Because of the current situation of the Engineering Educational System it has been considered the quality of all its students/the individual components have been noticed that the awareness on the importance of education. It is a foundation for the development and growth of the developing country like India. India is not strong enough. The graduates who passing out from the Engineering Educational Institutions have to satisfy the trendy, modern and high standard requirements of the industry which is really expected and needed by the industry. In today's showground the most common term/talk all come across is *recession*. It is mainly leads a result to a layoffs and increase in unemployment.

The campus is a place where the stakeholders (students) can get exposure to the peer group and also to the corporate. Industry Internship is the most identical and benefited opportunity to the students who can get the experiences for the lifetime. It acts as a prelude to the placement time. This internship programs is unlike dissertation and thesis. It is not just like the preparation of report. Actually it is about the using of the experiences of the working with the co-workers from various backgrounds. This internship is also gives an out picture of the corporate world, understanding the job functions with the multiple aspects of the growth in the specific function and the communicating aspects with the various functions. The research study is all about the collection/the pool of knowledge. Getting knowledge and learning is the two way communication³. The experiential learning and the practical approach of the learning is needed at the time/present. The theories will not be adopted for the day to day changing corporate world. It has been imparted for ages which are not even relevance for the fast changing today's corporate world. In the modern day, the students are given permission and liberty to question the classroom teachings and the institutes have become melting pots of ideas gradually

¹ Gray Dessler (2003) Human Resource Management, Pearson Education, Singapore, pg no.89, 187, 241.

² <http://blog.careesma.in/>

³ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Campus_placement

which had led to the creation of various successful startups. So the research studies help the students to decipher their plan of actions immediately. The research study is the most vital tool for the persons to become primary sources of information and the knowledge. To become a master in a particular subject/streamlining in an area of interest is the need of today.

Coimbatore is a major educational hub. The first college of Coimbatore, Government Arts College, was opened in 1875. The first engineering college in the city, the Arthur Hope College of Technology (now known as the Government College of Technology, Coimbatore), was started by G.D. Naidu in 1945 followed later by the private engineering colleges like PSG College of Technology and Coimbatore Institute of Technology in the 1950s. The Air Force Administrative College, established in 1949, is the oldest training institute of the Indian Air Force. Coimbatore Medical College was opened in 1966 and also the city has another Government run ESIC Medical College. The Government law college was started functioning from 1978. The agricultural school established in 1868 was converted into a full-fledged agricultural university as Tamil Nadu Agricultural University in 1971 and the Sálim Ali Centre for Ornithology and Natural History was opened in 1990. As of 2016, the district is home to 6 universities, 78 engineering colleges, 3 medical colleges, 2 dental colleges, 35 polytechnics and 58 arts and science colleges. The city, houses two government run universities Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Bharathiar University, and four private universities. The city houses Government research institutes including the Central Institute for Cotton Research, Sugarcane Breeding Research Institute, Institute of Forest Genetics and Tree Breeding (IFGTB), Indian Council of Forestry Research and Education and Tamil Nadu Institute of Urban Studies.

Operational Definitions:

The recruitment is “an optimistic process of surfing for the prospective workers and stimulating them to apply for the works in the entity. Whenever more number of persons are applying for the job, there will be a better scope for recruiting the right person for the right job at the right time at the right place”.

Campus Recruitment is “a program of job placement and the activities of this campus recruitment is administered by the Educational Institutions for graduating the students. The perspective workers typically visit the institutions’ campuses to meeting and recruiting the outstanding or the standard graduating students for the job openings. Normally, the job fairs have been conducted regularly which are the vital component of the Campus Recruitment Program and it facilitate the interviews and sessions of information between the graduating students and the perspective workers”⁴.

Reviews of Related Literatures:

A study conducted by Suresh Kumar N^{*}, Prasanth MK^{**}, Ajith Sundaram^{***5} entitled on “Campus Placements in Kerala – An empirical study at the selected Engineering Colleges in Kerala”. They inferred their study as the basic skills which are acquired by the students at school. It has an overall impact in molding the students’ career. After a particular stage, the extracurricular activities like arts, sports, games and technical events has an impact on the personality development of the students. It also increases the employability of them. The medium of instruction is more important component apart from the quality of teaching at various stages of selection process. The amount of drop outs in the stage of Screening test and the Group discussion which is called as the first and second stage is the highest in the process of selection. The interest level of the students whose guardian in various professionals, business and salaried are differ in campus placements. There is an associated relationship between the percentage of marks obtained by the students and number of placement drives attended by the students, the number of times the candidate have cleared the group discussion and the percentage of marks obtained by the candidate and the number of times the candidate have cleared the group discussion. The study concludes that, it is probably possible that the personality and the emotional temperament have the influence on the abilities in academic, and, the regardless variations and classification in language. There is some association between the academic performance and the characteristics of the students. It is certainly in need for more research study which is on the effectiveness of using various measures for the academic placement as well as the guidance on the potential uses of assessments of non-cognitive.

Hadass (2004)⁶ has conducted a research study on the effect of internet recruiting on the matching workers and the human resource managers. The Human Resource managers has developed a model of recruitment in which the seekers of jobs who have the private information about their educational qualification for the various jobs, entities and firms possessing the imperfect technologies of screening. The study concludes that the model has examined that the usage of the personnel data from a multinational manufacturing firm with more than 15,000 employees. The application of the e-recruitment was introduced to reduce the applications costs to the employees and screening technology for firms were improving. The researcher has concluded that

⁴ Porter, M. E. (1985). *The competitive advantage*. New York, NY: Free Press.

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⁶ Hadass, Yael S. (2004), “The Effect of Internet Recruiting on the Matching of Workers and HR Managers”, Available at SSRN: <http://ssrn.com/abstract=497262>

the firms may apply the e-recruitment strategies. It is because of the direct reduction in the costs of the recruitment and because of the competition among the Human resource Managers for the qualified and right hires.

Campus Hiring Process:

The process of Campus Hiring is refers to that any effort taken by the prospective management/employers to recruit the students from the college campuses which usually giving the priority to the graduates. The campus recruitment is used by the employers for attracting and screening the students for the varieties of positions. It can be as internship and as a full time basis. Sometimes, this recruitment process can take places in the form of small events which can be sponsored by any one or a few industry representatives. In some other cases, the educational institutions and the enterprises/industries collaborate to make a campus level job fairs which can attract many potential employers and/or employees. The businesses are the most active recruiters. But the graduate schools, non-profit organizations and the government also engaging themselves for the campus recruiting process. There is a record of short supply in the year 2011 of graduates especially in technical fields. The employers using different way of recruiting process to attract the best and brightest persons. Students at Engineering Colleges with the reputation Excellency in certain fields are in high demand and they are particularly in recruiting efforts at these educational institutions are very intense in frequently. The recruiters target is not only on the students who are the graduates and also interested in connecting the graduates students who have at least one year of education remaining and advanced undergraduates. These students are often expecting and sought after the internship. The internships are useful for the students which providing the experience in the real world business and it creates useful contacts. It also gives the benefit to employers too. It providing the employers both inexpensive skilled workers and offers a new insight into where the students are recruiting for the permanent employment⁷.

The tactics taken by the employers in the campus recruitment process is varying from one field to another. It usually a mixture of screening and advertising. The persons/representatives from recruiters will be provided with snacks, dinners which they put on shows to pique the student's curiosity and distribute swage. This is all an attempt to attract the interest of the students. The job fairs/festive bringing the students and recruiters together. The recruiters vie for the attention of promising the candidates in good number of years. In sinewy years, the recruiters have selected only the most promising of candidates. The campus recruitment process ends with a formal interview process. And the institutions often have the facilities were the job providers can interview the students. Many students may under to the process of interview entirely and also the recruiting process before they attend in their higher studies. It is particularly when the need of new graduates outpaces the supply and some of the students may get their job offers before getting their graduation⁸.

Emerging Trends of Campus Recruitment:

Using of Mobile Phone Technology to the Educational Institutions' Campus Visits: It is very easy to connect with millennial talent with the help of technology-based communication in a meaningful way. According to the survey of Robert Walters, it is identified that 85 per cent of Gen Y using their smartphones when their job hunting. There is numerous ways for the employers to connect with the college graduates by using the mobile phone technologies. The management/employers can use the mobile business card apps, can create a new mobile version for their own career pages and/or they even may create an app in mobile which is exclusively for the postings of job.

Recruiting the Interns and Process of Hiring Internally from the Internship: The better way to the employers which can guarantee their hire top talented is by intern hire. It is in fact, the source of one hire study reveals that out of 100 per cent 42 per cent of openings are guaranteed/filled by the internal movement. This internal hires can be done by the employers as a priority to be given by hiring the interns after completion of their internships. The same study opined that out of 100 per cent respondents 32 per cent of the internship holders accepted to become a full time job holders in the same company. So whenever the employers conducting/attending the engineering colleges for career fairs, they should switch the gears of mind and make their focus on hiring interns into the long term talent.

Using the Social Media as a Key to Tap into the Talent Communities: Now-a-days the social media placing a vital role in all of the human lives. Millennial job hunters are using a wide variety of Social Medias for their career advancement and applying the same for their internships and jobs. A study conducted in the year 2014 revealed that out of 100 per cent respondents, the 33 per cent of the respondents being college graduates who searching their job through the social media. In order to reach out the millennial talent persons, the management/the employers should use the social media which is connecting the college students easily (like Twitter, Facebook and LinkedIn). Many employers says that the social media are significantly having the influence on their hiring decisions when the hiring entry level professions.

⁷ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Campus_placement

⁸ Impact of Unemployment on Engineering Graduates in Recession study by Chandra Sekhar Patro, B.Lohit.

The Usage of Niche Job Sites and Benefiting By Its Advantages: When the employers hiring the young talents the mass job boards are becoming outdated quickly. Some studies revealed that many of the employers are planning to post their job offers in job boards in less in level, but they are mainly focusing more on the sites of job niche. When sourcing hires many respondents (employers) who says that they found the candidates on these sites. With the help of niche groups they employers can reach good number of Gen Y talent by posting their job opportunities.

Campus Recruitment Program as Remote: This has become a top trend at present which is saving the cost and time of visiting the educational institutions physically. Which this 'Remote Campus Recruitment Program', the employers can get a pre-qualifiers who done internally which to get only the interested candidates to apply for the job. It is very useful for the employers instead of locating/visiting a bunch of top universities/educational institutions. Simulations, online assessments, live video interviews through remote and contests are being used by the employers for hiring the best students and intern assessment.

Referrals by Campus: College students have a good connection on social media even across universities. The recruiters can use the recruiting referral models to get referrals from the colleges, interns, top college students and employees.

College Employment Brand: It is a critical task for the employers branding strategy to have a targeted college employment brand. This brand ('college employer brand') and value proposition have to develop enough for the deepest penetration in the college campus. The brand name popular in the campuses can be maintained by keeping a couple of 'campus specific reward contests'.

Maintaining the Good Campus Relations: It is very crucial task to the employers to maintain the campus relation for the success of campus recruiting. It is because of today's campus environment. It is highly recommended to the companies must maintain a good and to build a better relationship with the staff, administrators of educational institutions and should engage with colleges, universities and other educational institutions through the program of 'campus connect', 'internship', training programs, MOU and guest lectures.

Policy of Talent Can Exist Anywhere: The competencies and values of talents today has been aligned its culture with the values of organizations. The line of Tier 2 and Tier 3 becomes slowly dissolving. These categories of jobs are being offered and sometime both this categories could overlap⁹.

Industry Interface in Campus Recruitment:

In India there are more than 4,000 Engineering Educational Institutions are providing the Technical Education for their students. The GHRDC (Global Human Resource Development Centre) who is the highly research oriented organization have been started as the pioneer in starting the process of rating the Engineering Educational Institutions and also ranking of it. It has surveyed the top Engineering Educational Institutions which is across in India. The methodology followed by the GHRDC covers all the vital dimensions and the factors of parameters of an Engineering Educational Institution. The common indicator of parameters used by the GRDC is to evaluate the colleges is by its academic programmes, research and consultancy, staff members, infrastructure and the *placement*. The key indicator and the parameters were investigated, identified and the weightages were allotted to the parameters. For more regressive factors and the analysis by quantitative and qualitative assessments, the tool of parameters has been sub-divided into a good number of sub-parameters. The GHRDC has taken around 460 to each college and they have listed top colleges according to their study. It has been published by the GHRDC in social websites. This has been prepared on the base on the *placement records* of the Engineering Educational Institutions. The each college's image will guide the uses to find out the score of the college's *placement*¹⁰.

Disputes of Campus Recruitment:

It is a highly accepted crisis which we are passing through is confidence for careers and skills. In olden days, the colleges were churning its volumes and the industries were also picking the same number of volumes is over. The companies were realized that investing the students to retrain for around six to nine months may not be a compelling proposition of business. The B and C rung campuses are the biggest challenges for the employer in the quality of the talent available. The communication skills and the knowledge in technical side in this kind of campuses is not good and even raw. The value of talent is getting down when there is a huge number of passing out. But when the situation for the employers which make them to hiring the talents from A rung campuses, the candidates may come with high expectations and selective. They may not and/or not willing to work in the locations of remote area. Therefore, the tenure duration of this kind of students at the job is very small in level. In some campuses, the desire at the initial is like a slog and their learning is getting decrease which is being a depressing factor of their talent. For coping this, the management should be more active in facilitating them at colleges. The crucial students should be groomed as the expectations and the standards of industry. New advanced technology what we are using now is not a big problem in programming for the new students. The main problem/challenge faced by the recruiters while recruiting the new fresher is the attitude of

⁹ Stone, R. (2005). Human resource management. Milton, John Wiley & Sons Australia Ltd.

¹⁰ Townley, B. (1994). Reframing Human Resource Management: Power, Ethics and the Subject at Work. London, Sage Publications.

the fresher. In the starting time, some candidates are overly ambitious/aimed but some others are confused. Many candidates will select a particular industry which is assumed to be a very glamorous (like IT industry). But the reality is far from this assumption. It is a general state that there is a major generations who have the generation gap which should be filled. This can happen only if the fresher from the Engineering Educational Institutions are willing to adopt themselves and adjust their new environment and surroundings. Whenever the students are struggling with adopting themselves with the needs, demands and expectations of the industry then the recruiting program from the Engineering Educational Institutions is getting failure.

Whenever the employers want to get succeed in the recruitment process and the demand of the college recruitment process must be reengineered. The talent is the key where the demand is continuously increase dramatically. The recruiting budgets of corporate colleges and their processes is being stagnant over the last decades. Even though, the colleges itself and their expectations of their students are being changed dramatically. But in the case of the colleges who have the reengineered recruiting model should move its process beyond a focus on the career centers and should increase the capacities to the area of remote college recruiting, recruiting passive students, recruiting students from online engineering universities, global college recruiting. The use of market research to the complete understand of the process of job search and the new generation's expectations of grades.

Analysis of the Study:

Table 1: Ranking on Skill needed for the students to fulfill the corporate recruitment trends and challenges

S.No	Factors	Mean	S.D.	Ranks
1.	Ability to speak a foreign language	2.97	0.14	I
2.	Customer orientation – friendly and caring	2.92	0.24	II
3.	Effective verbal communication skills	2.58	0.37	III
4.	Effective written communication skills	2.57	0.42	IV
5.	Leadership and management	2.54	0.55	V
6.	The ability to work in a team	2.53	0.72	VI
7.	Numeracy	2.44	0.60	VII
8.	Professionalism	2.38	0.65	VIII
9.	Technical and computer skills	2.29	0.62	IX
10.	The ability to solve the problems	2.13	0.72	X

Source: Primary source of data collection

From the rank test, it is inferred that the majority of the Skills needed for the students are Ability to speak a foreign language, followed by Customer orientation – friendly and caring, Effective verbal communication skills and etc.

Factor Analysis:

The following table illustrates the Skills needed for the students. Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity has been used as the Pre-analysis testing for the suitability of the entire sample for the factor analysis. The result of KMO and Bartlett's Test is found greater than 0.70. Hence, the collected data is fit for the factor analysis. Further, the large values of Bartlett's sphericity test (4.7853, df=91, Sig=0.000) and KMO statistics (0.954) indicated the appropriateness of factor analysis i.e., the sample was adequate. Table 1 shows the results of the factor analysis carried out using the Skill needed for the students.

Table 2: KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy		.954
Bartlett's Test of Sohericity	Approx. Chi-Square	4.7853
	D.f.	91
	Significance	.000

Source: (Collected and computed through the questionnaire)

Table 3: Factor Analysis

Impediments	Factor 1	Factor 2
Ability to speak a foreign language	0.212	0.777
Customer orientation – friendly and caring	0.376	0.733
Effective verbal communication skills	0.316	0.691
Effective written communication skills	0.162	0.801
Leadership and management	0.822	0.242
The ability to work in a team	0.734	0.361
Numeracy	0.658	0.456
Professionalism	0.826	0.245
Technical and computer skills	0.875	0.188
The ability to solve problems	0.786	0.277
Eigen Values	8.094	1.244

% of Variance Explained	57.813	8.882
Cumulative % of Variance	57.813	66.695

Source: (Collected and computed through the questionnaire)

Two factors are identified by locating the Eigen values greater than unity. Skills needed for the students which have a component loading of 0.7 and above are said to be significant factors of employability skills. From the rotated component matrix Table 3 can be seen that “Leadership and management” (0.875), “The ability to work in a team” (0.826), “Professionalism” (0.822), “Technical and computer skills” (0.786), and “The ability to solve the problems” (0.734), have a component loading of 0.7 and above. Hence, these five variables form first factor. In the second factor two, “Ability to speak a foreign language” (0.801), “Customer orientation – friendly and caring” (0.77), and “Effective written communication skills” (0.733), are found to be significant.

Findings of the Study:

From the rank test, it is inferred that the majority of the Skills needed for the students are Ability to speak a foreign language, followed by the Customer orientation – friendly and caring, Effective verbal communication skills and etc.

Factor one contributes to a tune of 57.813 per cent towards the factors of employability skills. The other factor contributes namely, 8.882 Skills needed for the students in their order. The total cumulative percentage of contribution by these two factors towards the Skill needed for the students is 66.695 per cent.

Suggestions for the Study:

- ✓ The candidates from the Engineering Educational Institutions should probe the campus interview’s nature. It is not possible to the candidates to find the exact reasons for the interview. Sometimes, the recruiters may looking out the right candidate for their vacancy and/or they may merely fishing the good resumes. But, when a recruiter faces the interview, they can ask the recruiter about the purpose of the specific vacancies that they are recruiting for. Then the candidates can fix the level of efforts to do for the interview.
- ✓ The candidates should do a research on the company’s profile.
- ✓ There should be a strong platform of collaboration with the company and the college. The portals like website links may help to reach out the better company HRs.
- ✓ The Engineering Educational Institutions should create the awareness in the students by giving the latest news and developments related the top recruiting companies.
- ✓ The institutions should make the students to use the career fair platforms.
- ✓ It should make the students to be well prepared in their projects and internships.
- ✓ It is the duty of the placement cell of Engineering Educational Institutions to give a complete knowledge on the placement recruiting process such as, tests, group discussion, and personal interviews.

Conclusion:

The program of the Campus Interviews are the most vital part of the students’ life in their college studies. It creates a future for them. The Engineering Educational Institutions should prepare the students as soon as the graduation time near and the students have to be prepared for the interview as like one of the fine exams. The chances of success in the interview will determine the future career of the students. It will create a good break for the college campus which will give an eases way ahead in the future!

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